

Factor Affecting Students's Speaking Performance At Ho Chi Minh University Of Food Industry

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Abstract

The development of spoken language is also seen as one of the most challenging aspects of language learning (Brown & Yule, 1983). In fact, it is hard for many language learners to express themselves in the target language in spoken language. Every student has his or her own issues. The aim of this study was to investigate the students at the Faculty of Foreign Language's talking problems and the factors influencing their speaking performance. The research subjects were 100 students and 10 teachers of HUFI. The questionnaires and class observation are two main methods used in this study. Some recommendations were made based on results from the study. The study was intended to help students develop their speaking skills

Keywords: Problem of Speaking; Speaking Skills; Developing Speaking.

1. Introductions

Speaking tends to become the most important skills of all 4 skills (listening, speaking, reading, and writing), as people who learn a language are usually referred to as language speakers (Ur, 1996). The primary goal of all English language teaching should be to give learners the ability to use English in communication effectively and correctly (Davies & Pearse, 1998). Not all language students, however, can communicate fluently and accurately after many years of studying English, because they lack the necessary knowledge. The students at HUFI, they are not good at English. They can pass tests quickly, but they find it hard to communicate in English. It is important to find ways to help the students develop their speaking skills and help them solve their problems. In addition, the teachers need to learn the factors influencing the speaking performance of their students so that they can work with these factors and help the students enhance their speaking performance. Nevertheless, no work on these areas has been done at this school until now.

The current study addresses two issues:

1. *What are the problems that the students at Ho Chi Minh City University Of Food Industry encounter when they learn to speak English?*
2. *What are the factors that affect student' speaking performance at HUFI?*

13. Literature Review

Communicative Competence

We need linguistic ability, sufficient vocabulary and syntax mastery to speak in a foreign language (Nunan, 1999). Linguistic competence, however, is not enough for those who would like to

communicate competently in another language. According to Nunan (1999), the speaker needs communication skills that include not only language skills but also a range of other sociolinguistic and conversational skills that help him / her know how to tell whom and when. Johnson (1995) argues that students of second language need communicative skills to participate in and learn from their experience in the classroom.

At first, in 1980 Canale and Swain classified communicative competence into three parts, namely grammatical competence, sociolinguistic competence and strategic competence. Then the fourth component called discourse competence was added by Canale and Swain in 1983 (Kumaravadivelu, 2006). Communicative competence is said to have only three components in the Common European Framework (2001) including linguistic competence, sociolinguistic competence and pragmatic competence. Communicative skills are identified in this study with four components including linguistic skills, sociolinguistic skills, relational skills and strategic skills.

Factors affecting speaking performance

To help students solve difficulties in learning to speak, the teachers need to find out factors that influence their speech performance. Speaking performance of students may be influenced by factors that come from performance conditions (time pressure, preparation, performance level and amount of support), affective factors (such as motivation, trust and anxiety), listening skills, and input during speaking activities.

Performance conditions

In a number of circumstances the students perform a speaking task. Nation & Newton (2009) think that conditions of performance will influence the efficiency of speaking. Nation & Newton (2009) suggests four forms of success conditions including time pressure, preparation, performance level and amount of support.

Affective factors

Probably the affective side of the learner is one of the most important influences on language learning success or failure (Oxford, 1990). Krashen(1982) notes that a number of affective variables have been reported to be correlated with study performance in the learning of second language over the past decade, but most of these studies investigated the three categories: motivation, self-confidence and anxiety.

Listening ability

You can't improve communication skills until we improve listening skills (Doff, 1998). To have a good discussion, the students must understand what is being said to them. Shumin (1997) shares Doff's(1998) ideas by explaining that when one person is speaking, the other responds by attending by listening. Each speaker essentially plays both the role of a listener and a speaker. Therefore one will definitely not respond if he / she can't understand what is being said. This means that communicating is closely related to listening.

Feedback during speaking activities

Most students want to give their teachers feedback on their performance, and expect them to do so. All talk production, however, should not be dealt with in the same way. Harmer (1991) argues that the decisions made by the teachers on how to react to the performance of the students will depend on the lesson stages, the activities, the types of errors made, and the particular student making the mistake. If the teachers correct if a question occurs, it will disrupt the conversational flow as well as the intent of the speaking activity (Harmer, 1991). If the students are constantly being corrected, they will find this very demotivating and be afraid to speak.

Speaking problems

There are some speaking issues for Ur (1996) that teachers may experience in getting students to talk in the classroom. These are inhibition, lack of current knowledge, low or uneven involvement, and use of mother tongue.

The first problem is the students often experience is inhibition. When students attempt to say anything in a language they are often inhibited in the classroom. They worry about making mistakes, being afraid of criticism or losing face. They're timid about the attention their speech attracts. Littlewood (2007) claims that a classroom in a foreign language will quickly build anxiety and inhibitions.

Second, learners sometimes lament they can't think of anything to say and they don't have the energy to speak out. Rivers (1968) claims that the learners have little to say, perhaps because the instructor has chosen a subject that is unfit for him or that he knows very little about. It is difficult for many students to respond when the teachers ask them to say something in a foreign language because they may have little ideas about what to say, which vocabulary to use, or how to use the grammar correctly (Baker & Westrup, 2003).

Another problem with speaking class is the poor or unequal attendance. Every student will have very little speaking time in a large group, because only one participant can speak at a time so the others can hear him / her. Some learners seem to dominate while others say very little or not at all.

Lastly, when all or a number of learners share the same mother tongue, they prefer to use it because they find it easier. Harmer (1991) suggests several explanations why mother tongue is used in class by students. Secondly, when the students are asked to have a conversation about a subject they are unable to address, they should use their own language if they wish to say something about the subject. Another explanation is that the use of mother-tongue is something easy to do. Additionally, using the first language to explain something to another if the teachers don't encourage it. Finally, if teachers often use the language of the students, the students will feel comfortable in doing so.

Previous studies

Some preceding studies related to this study will be reviewed in this part of the study. Such studies were conducted to establish the factors that influence the speaking performance of the students and the speaking problems of the students. Park & Lee (2005) looks at the relationships between the anxiety, self-confidence and speaking performance of second language learners. The study participants were one hundred and thirty-two Korean college students who were enrolled in the English communication classes. The results of their study showed that the level of anxiety between learners was negatively linked to their oral performance.

Tanveer (2007) examines the factors that trigger language anxiety for twenty language learners in learning speaking skills and the impact of anxiety on target language communication, and its finding

is close to what Park & Lee (2005) points out. The findings indicated that the feelings of stress, anxiety, or nervousness of the students may hinder their language ability to learn and perform. He quotes that "the greater the anxiety, the less the performance"

Feyten (1991) conducted a study to investigate whether there is a connection between listening skills and foreign language skills, listening skills and comprehension skills in the foreign language, and listening skills and oral language skills. The findings indicate that there is a major overlap between listening skills and foreign language skills; between listening skills and comprehension skills in foreign languages; and between listening skills and oral skills in foreign languages.

His study findings show a close correlation between listening comprehension and language skills. The higher the listening score, he says, the better the speaking score. Lukitasari (2008) conducted a study that focused on the approaches of the students in resolving speech difficulties in speaking class. Her study results indicate that the students faced some speaking problems including resistance, nothing to say, poor or unequal participation and use of mother tongue in speaking class.

14. Methodology

14.1. Participants of the study

For this analysis the research instruments used to collect data were questionnaires and class observation. The questionnaires were given to both the Department 's ten teachers and 100 students. The questionnaires for teachers were made up of ten questions designed in English. The questions of the students were made up of 10 closed-questions in English. I used class evaluation in tandem with questionnaires to see how the teachers conducted speaking lessons, how the students responded, and what difficulties the students actually experienced in speaking lessons. For each class, I observed two classes, two periods. Everything observed, heard, and experienced during class observation was recorded carefully in detail in the following observation sheet.

Time	Content	Teacher's activities	Students' activities
	1. Warm up		
	2. Pre-speaking		
	3. While-speaking		
	4. Post- speaking		
	5. Homework		

14.2. Intrusment

The research instrument employed to collect data for this study were questionnaires and class observation. The questionnaires were delivered to 100 students of Hufi. The students' questions consisted of 10 closed-questions designed in English.

14.3. Procedeure For Conducting The Questionnaire Survey

The questionnaires were planned, and the questionnaire for the students was then translated into Vietnamese. The researcher clearly explained the purpose of administering the questionnaire by

finding the speaking problems of the students, the factors affecting their performance, and finding ways to improve the speaking skills of the students. The teachers then told the students to finish it off. On the same day, in their twenty-minute break at staff room, ten sheets of the teachers' questionnaire were distributed to ten English teachers. I gave the teachers oral directions and descriptions in details before replying to the questionnaire to prevent any misunderstandings. Then, they collected completed questionnaires.

14.4. Data Analysis Procedure

The quantitative data from the questionnaires have been analyzed using Excel programme. The descriptive statistics of the frequencies and percentages were used to answer the two research questions. The qualitative data was extracted from evaluation of the class. It described in detail what happened in each observed class. The researcher also spoke about certain groups' high and weak points.

15. Results

Questionnaire Result

15.1. What are the factors that affect their speaking performance?

Most teachers (90%) agreed that topical knowledge had an impact on the speaking performance of students. 80% of teachers felt that the ability to listen had an effect on the speaking performance of students. The same number of teachers (8/10) perceived motivation to speak as important factors influencing the speaking performance of the students. 70% of teachers referred to feedback as factors that influenced speaking performance during speaking activities and trust. 40% of teachers felt that their students' speaking success often influenced time for training and motivation to perform well.

Nearly half of them (47%) viewed the pressure to perform well as the most influential factor when asked to select the factors affecting their speaking performance among the listed factors. 40% of students thought their speaking performance could be affected by anxiety. 38% per cent agreed that the time required to carry out a speaking task would affect the outcome. Through 81% of the students, topical awareness was considered to be an influencing factor. 41% of them thought their speaking performance might be influenced by motivation to speak. 62% students said their speaking performance was affected by confidence. Just only a small number of the students (27%) thought that time for preparation could affect their performance.

In short, the findings showed a number of factors affecting the speaking performance of the students were present. A majority of teachers were says the speaking performance of the students had been influenced by topical knowledge. The next two main factors listed were listening skills and speech motivation. In addition, feedback from the teachers during the speaking activities was also reported to affect the speaking performance of the students. Finally, confidence was deemed a factor that influenced the performance of students.

The findings from the student questionnaire were very close to those of the teachers, most of the students felt the topical information influenced their speaking performance. The next big aspect was ability to listen. The students also felt they had to be sure that they could perform well. Last but not least, the students indicated that feedback during speaking activities and the desire to perform well affected their performance too.

15.2. What are the problem that the students at HUF1 encounter when they learn speaking?

The teachers were required to pick the speaking issues their students encounter. Seven problems were provided for the teachers to choose from. All the teachers decided that in speaking class, their students spoke very little or no at all. 90% of teachers thought there was nothing their students could think of. 80% of teachers said their students often used Vietnamese in English lessons, rather than English. The same number of teachers (8/10) thought there was no motivation for the students to express themselves in English. The students were afraid of criticism or losing face to seven teachers. 60% of teachers claimed the students were concerned about making mistakes. Half of the teachers said the students were shy at speaking class.

When asked about the problems they encountered in speaking classes, a majority of the students (74%) were very much in agreement that they spoke very little or no. In English speaking, 73% of

students were concerned about making mistakes. 71% of them said they couldn't think of anything. 70% of the students said they also spoke Vietnamese. 61% of students claimed they were not motivated to express themselves in speaking class. 48% of the students were shy of the attention their speech attracted when taking part in speaking activities. 28% agreed that they feared criticism or losing face.

In short, the results from the questionnaires given to both the teachers and the students revealed that they faced several difficulties when the students learn to speak. The most common speaking problem, according to the teachers, was that the students spoke very little or nothing in classroom speaking. Most teachers said there was little that the students could think of to say. In addition, they often used Vietnamese and had little desire to speak out. The student questionnaire findings were almost similar to those from the instructor questionnaire. The students reported that in speaking class they spoke very little, or nothing. They couldn't think of anything to say so they used Vietnamese most of the time. A substantial number of students also claimed they were afraid of criticism or losing face. They had no ability to express themselves in English

Observation results

Class observations were conducted to see how students actually performed and what problems they experienced in speaking classes. The most common problems in the groups described are as follows:

- ✚ Students were not given adequate time to prepare for the task of speaking before the task was performed and to fulfill their duties.
- ✚ The students were not always willing to express their thoughts in English when asked to work in groups. Some of them were strongly interested but the others talked a little, or not at all.
- ✚ When debated in groups they preferred to use Vietnamese.
- ✚ The other students in the class did not listen attentively while the students were doing performances. When their classmates talked they even chatted with the people next to them.
- ✚ The students looked very nervous when they were talking before the class. They did not know what to do at times, so stayed silent.
- ✚ They read that which they wrote on a sheet of paper. To speak naturally, they didn't know the mechanisms and vocabulary.
- ✚ If the students made errors they were stopped and corrected by the teacher.
- ✚ In a span of forty-five minutes, the students had to do several things. They were always in a rush because they had limited time provided for each mission.

16. Discussion

Generally speaking, data from the questionnaire for teachers, the questionnaire for students, and class observation were conspiring.

The factors that affect students' speaking performance

As for the first research issue, the findings showed that there were a number of factors influencing the speaking performance of the students. A majority of teachers said the speaking performance of the students had been affected by topical knowledge. The next two important factors mentioned were listening skills and speech motivation. In addition, feedback from the teachers during the speaking activities was also reported to affect the speaking performance of the students. Eventually, trust was seen as a factor affecting the success of the students.

The findings from the student questionnaire were very close to those of the teachers, most of the students felt the topical information influenced their speaking performance. The next big aspect was willingness to listen. The students also felt they had to be sure that they should perform well. Last but not least, the students reported that feedback during speaking activities and the pressure to perform well affected their performance too.

The data obtained from class observations revealed that the speaking performance of the students is also affected by preparation time. In all the four lessons observed, the students were given little time to prepare so their performance was not good

The problems that the students at HUPI encounter when they learn speaking

In the current study, the findings from the questionnaires delivered to both the teachers and the students showed that when the students learn speaking, they encountered many problems. The most common speaking problem, according to the teachers, was that the students spoke very little or nothing in classroom speaking. Most teachers said there was little that the students could think of to say. In addition, they often used Vietnamese and had little desire to speak out.

The student questionnaire findings were almost the same as those from the teachers questionnaire. The students reported that in speaking class they spoke very little, or nothing. They couldn't think of anything to say so they used Vietnamese most of the time. A substantial number of students also claimed they were afraid of criticism or losing face. They had no ability to express themselves in English.

Also reported were some more talk problems that the students experienced in the observed classrooms. The first problem was that the students frequently translated the details into Vietnamese in the textbook before they did the tasks. The second problem was that much of the speaking performance of the students sounded awkward, and when they spoke they did not know the concepts and vocabulary. They just looked on and read their book. Additionally, uneven participation in all the lessons observed was also considered another issue. Some students actively participated in the classroom activities while the others did so unwillingly.

In general, it was clear from the study findings that the students faced several difficulties in the speaking class. In addition, there have been other factors that have led to their performance and weakness in speaking activities. The existing teaching and speaking skills learning at the Ho Chi Minh City University Of Food Industry had to be improved overall.

17. Conclusions

As mentioned above, the purpose of this study was to investigate the problems experienced by students at the Ho Chi Minh City University of Food Industry in speaking lessons and the factors affecting their speaking performance. The study results indicate that the students faced many problems, such as:

1. They spoke very little or not at all.
2. They couldn't think of anything to say.
3. They used Vietnamese rather than English when talking in groups or in pairs.
4. Their participation was low or uneven.
5. They didn't have the motivation to express themselves.
6. They were afraid of criticism or loss.
7. They used to translate the information in the textbook into Vietnamese before they spoke

8. when they spoke, they looked at their manual

The findings also show that there were many factors influencing students speaking performance as follows:

1. Contextual knowledge.
2. Ability to listen.
3. Motivation to speak.
4. Input from teachers when speaking.
5. Confidence.
6. Desire to perform well.
7. Preparation time.

Based on the study results, some recommendations were made at the Ho Chi Minh City University of Food Industry for both the teachers and the students. As for the teachers, they can first enhance the conditions of success by allowing their students time to plan for a speaking assignment, teaching students how to use mind maps to generate ideas, and giving students enough time to execute their tasks.

Second, they should help their students overcome inhibition and shyness by having friendly, helpful, and cooperative behaviors to make students feel comfortable speaking in the classroom, reminding students not to worry about making mistakes and giving them clear instructions and sufficient guidance. Second, the teacher should personalize the subjects in the textbook and simplify them to make them simpler, more interesting and important to their lives. In addition, speaking skills should be included in assessments and examinations because the students would be more inspired to learn speaking skills as they are being tested. Another suggestion is that teachers should provide more opportunities for students to speak English in a classroom through some speaking activities that require students to speak. In addition, the teachers should carefully decide when and how to correct the errors of the students, so that the students are not afraid to make mistakes and the conversation flow of the students is not destroyed. The teacher will also allow the students to take part in speaking events. Lastly, teachers should create an English-speaking environment by encouraging students to use English in the classroom to make it a habit to allow them to watch English movies or videos, and teachers should also frequently use English in the classroom to make students more exposed to the language.

For students, the importance of speaking skills should first be understood. Their knowledge of their studies can motivate them to learn. Secondly, they should practice speaking English more frequently outside the classroom by doing the speaking tasks with their classmates in the textbook at home, joining a speaking club where they can use English to communicate and speak alone in front of a mirror. Finally, instead of using the Vietnamese they should use English in the class to make it a habit.

Hopefully, the study at the Ho Chi Minh City University of Food Industry can contribute to helping students improve English learning.

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Appendices

Appendix For Teachers

Part I: Information

1. Sex

- Male
- Female

2. Ages

- 20-24 years
- 25-30 years
- 31-35 years
- 36- 40

3. Educational Graduate

- Bachelor's degree
- Master's degree
- Other.....

4. How many years have you taught English?

- 1-3 years
- 4-7 years
- 8- 10 years
- More than 10 years

Part II: Factors affecting students in speaking and the speaking problems

5. How are the performance conditions in speaking class?

How are the Speaking Class performance condition	Yes	No
Are the students given plenty of time to do a talk task?		
Should the students prepare for a mission before they carry out the assignment?		
Is there pressure from the students to perform well?		
Are listeners patient, understanding, supportive and sympathetic?		

6. How are your students in speaking class?

- Motivated
- Anxious
- Confident

7. How about your students' listening skills?

- Very bad
- Bad
- Normal
- Good
- Very good

8. What is your reaction when the students make mistakes during speaking?

- Stay calm, smile, and help them to do their homework.
- If students are unable to think about what to say, they will be motivated to do so
- Avoid the errors and fix them.
- Get irritated as the students start to make mistakes.
- Observe, listen to the students, write down points, and then provide feedback..

9. In your words, which of the following affecting your students' speaking ?

- | | |
|---|--|
| ☐ Time for preparation | ☐ Topical knowledge |
| ☐ Pressure to perform well | ☐ Listening ability |
| ☐ Listeners' support | ☐ Feedback during speaking activities |
| ☐ Motivation to speak | ☐ Time allowed to perform a speaking task |
| ☐ Confidence | |

10. Which speaking problems do your students encounter?

- | | |
|--|---|
| ☐ They are worried about making mistakes. | ☐ They have no motive to express themselves. |
| ☐ They are fearful of criticism or losing face. | ☐ They speak very little or not at all. |
| ☐ They cannot think of anything to say. | ☐ They use Vietnamese. |
| | ☐ They are shy. |

Appendix For Students

Part I: Information

1. Gender

- Male
- Female

2. Age

- Under 15
- 15-17
- 17-20

3. How long have you been learning English

- Under 1 year
- 2-4 years
- 4-7 years
- Over 7 years

Part II: Affecting students' speaking and speaking problems

4. How much do you like speaking English in class?

- Very much
- Rather
- Normal
- Little
- Not at all

5. How often do you use speaking outside the class environment?

- Always
- Usually
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never

6. Your opinion about the necessity of speaking skills to your career ?

- Very necessary
- Necessary
- Normal
- Unnecessary
- Very unnecessary

7. The performance conditions during speaking class?

Performance conditions	Yes	No
Are you given plenty of time to perform a speaking task?		
Do you prepare for a task before the task is performed?		

Do you have the pressure to perform well?		
Are the listeners patient, understanding, sympathetic and supportive?		

8. How do you feel in speaking class?

- Motivated
- Anxious
- Confident

9. Could you review your listening skills?

- Very bad
- Bad
- Normal
- Good
- Very good

10. How often do the teachers correct your mistakes while you are performing your tasks?

- Always
- Often
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never

11. Which factors affect your speaking skills?

- Time for preparation
- Pressure to perform well
- Listeners' support
- Motivation to speak
- Confidence
- Anxiety
- Topical knowledge
- Listening ability
- Time allowed to perform a speaking task

Other factors (please specify).....

12. Which problems do you encounter in learning speaking skill? (You can have more than one choice)

- You are worried about making mistakes.
- You are fearful of criticism or losing face.
- You cannot think of anything to say.
- You have no motivation to express yourselves.
- You speak very little or not at all.
- You use Vietnamese.
- You are shy.